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The Study on the Workplace-related Corporate Social Responsibility Practices

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to explore the challenges regarding the workplace area of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). Nowadays, organisations and their leaders are facing unprecedented pressures from both internal and external forces. Furthermore, there is a growing interest in understanding and managing issues related to sustainability. In these circumstances, organisations, regardless of their field of activity, have to implement responsible ways of doing business. Most CSR research focuses primarily on external areas: marketplace, environment, community, and external stakeholders: customers, suppliers, investors, government. Knowledge and digital economy and the fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) greatly influence human capital. Today, there is fierce competition in attracting and retaining the best employees – as critical stakeholders. Recruiting, developing, utilising and retaining a talented workforce has become a critical success factor. In this context, it is crucial to explore the workplace as an internal dimension of CSR. Our research methodology includes a theoretical analysis based on literature regarding this topic and an online survey based on a questionnaire. The conclusions and solutions highlighted at the end of the paper can support Human Resource managers and business leaders in addressing these challenges and developing knowledge and skills to generate long-term value for businesses, society and the environment. We anticipate that our findings will shed more light on CSR workplace practices that can be integrated into the business sustainability strategy.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Stakeholders, Employees, Workplace

Introduction

Nowadays, organisations and their leaders are facing unprecedented challenges generated by: increased competition; globalisation; shifts in demographics; global warming and climate change; emerging technologies; health issues; resource depletion; ecological concerns; and increasing customer demands. In this context, organisations need to focus on the economic added value and be concerned in adding both social and environmental value. Considering the issues regarding

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sustainability worldwide and in all industries, organisations have to implement more responsible ways of doing business. Social responsibility applies in all walks of life and all kinds of organisations, whether business oriented or not (Crowther & Seif, 2018). Considering the world's major economic, environmental and social challenges, responsible organisations are vital to our society.

Corporate social responsibility (csr) – some remarks

Nowadays, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has become not only a buzzword among academics and practitioners but also a key business practice and a responsible management approach. Corporate Social Responsibility can influence Corporate Reputation (CR), both having an important role in assuring a competitive advantage for corporations in a world of high global competitiveness (Endrikat et al., 2020).

Corporate Social Responsibility is a complex concept that may have different meanings in different cultures to various people, and its role can also be explored in connection with Total Quality Management and Corporate Green Performance (Abbas, 2020). Some authors use corporate responsibility as an umbrella term that captures the variety of ways in which a business's relationship with society is being defined, managed, and acted upon (Blowfield & Murray, 2014). Frequently, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) overlaps with similar or identical approaches, meanings, names and terms: social responsibility, corporate responsibility, corporate social performance (CSP), responsible business, corporate societal responsibility, corporate citizenship, business citizenship, sustainable and ethical business, sustainable, responsible business (SRB), corporate sustainability, sustainability, sustainable corporate development, public responsibility, corporate philanthropy, business ethics, etc. Recognition and understanding the intersection of economic, environmental, and social interests and attaining all three (Wang et al., 2020) are important challenges regarding CSR, under whose banner addresses some of the most important issues of the present and the future. Over time CSR has been defined in many ways, by different scholars and practitioners. We have a vast array of literature on CSR. Alexander Dahlsrud analysed 37 different definitions of CSR and concluded that, there are some confusion on how to define CSR and despite the efforts no clear and unbiased definition (Dahlsrud, 2008). In our previous researches we address CSR concept analysing significant definitions (Gorski, Fuciu, & Croitor, 2014; Gorski et al., 2016; Gorski, 2017). As a result, it is important to emphasise that different understandings of CSR concept have created sometimes not only misunderstandings, but also obstacle in the way organisations have approach CSR opportunities and challenges. The challenge is not to define Corporate Social Responsibility but rather to understand its social construction and integrate it in the business strategies. A strategic approach of corporate social responsibility is very important in order to aim business goals, to obtain performance and in the same time to communicate the efforts in social responsibility.

Employees – as internal stakeholders

According to Freeman Stakeholder Theory (Freeman, 1984), businesses have a responsibility to create value for their stakeholders to increase profits for the shareholders. Moreover, the executives have to consider the interests of different people and groups not in isolation but a systemic approach. In this complex world of sustainability, the balance rests in the hand of stakeholders and, more

importantly, in the value concepts that they employ or deploy (Hawkins, 2006; Goodman et al., 2017; Lee & Raschke, 2020).

Stakeholder groups can be divided into different criteria. Concerning organisational aspects, we can distinguish between internal and external stakeholders (Freeman, 1984; Harrison & John, 2013; Beringer et al., 2013; Cardwell, Williams, & Pyle, 2017). Internal stakeholders who include: employees, managers, owners/ shareholders, board of directors, and investors, have a relevant impact on organisational performance. CSR portfolio requires a holistic approach that considers and balances both internal and external stakeholders (Scheidler et al., 2016). It is critical to understand and treat employees as internal customers of companies' investments (Korschun et al., 2014). Studies emphasise that employees' management is significantly and positively associated with performance (Galbreath, 2006). Among stakeholder groups, employees are vital to any discussion regarding the origins and consequences of CSR (Aguilera, Rupp, Williams, & Ganapathi, 2007; Schaefer et al., 2020). Today, competition for the best employees is already as fierce or even more intense as competition for customers. We live and work in a knowledge-based economy in which a high-quality workforce is becoming a competitive advantage. Human capital is accountable for creating a sustainable competitive advantage (Ortega-Lapidera et al., 2019). Nowadays, not only organisational success but the wealth of nations is closely related to human capital. It has become more than just a fad, but a necessity for organisations to recognise the value and importance of employees, which have become a critical success factor. Attracting, utilising, and retaining talents who can add value is very important to excel and develop and maintain competitive advantages in a knowledge economy. A talented, quality workforce can be considered one of the organisation's assets and an important source of competitive advantage. In this context, most organisations are struggling to recruit, motivate, and develop talents.

Internal corporate social responsibility (i-csr) and the workplace

Some authors emphasise employees' involvement, as a major stakeholder, in the co-creation and implementation of the CSR process (Bolton et al., 2011). It is acknowledged that corporate social responsibility (CSR) has an external dimension (external CSR) and an internal one (internal CSR), and this both are related to internal and external stakeholders (Freeman, 1984; Werther & Chandler, 2010; Farooq et al., 2017; Jia et al., 2019). The actions taken by organisations to meet employees' expectations are closely related to internal CSR. Organisational fairness concerning employees, work safety, employees growth, and development are only some of the internal CSR actions (Jia et al., 2019). Employees at all levels are an important internal stakeholder group, directly involved in performing productive activities. Internal CSR is closely linked with employees' wellbeing - both psychological and physiological - and refers to the organisation's policies, practices, and actions in order to ensure a healthy and safe workplace, employee growth and development, work-life balance, employee relations, employee training, continuous educational programs, career and personal development, respect for human rights, equal opportunity, diversity, transparency, and other ingredients that could satisfy the expectations of employees. Some authors emphasise that CSR actions and practices centred on employees' wellbeing could increase the perceived respect (Brammer et al., 2007; Turker, 2009, Farooq et al., 2017).

Nowadays, the challenge of working together with five generations of employees – Silence (Traditionalist); Baby Boomers; Generation X; Generation Y or Millennial; Generation Z or "Generation 2020" – is not easy to manage. Organisational leaders and human resources

professionals should create workplaces that employees, especially top talent, will embrace (Meister & Willyerd, 2010; Kohntopp & McCann, 2020). Employees and customers expect similar CSR values. Employees request functional, economic, psychological, and ethical benefits from their employers (Mason & Simmons, 2014).

Knowledge economy and society, digital transformation and the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) – with the emergent and disruptive technologies (EDT) – have huge influences on human capital. Organisations are confronted with pressures and challenges, which require new competencies, knowledge and skills. The war for talents is here and is more intense than ever. Organisational success depends largely on their ability to attract, motivate and retain a talented pool of employees. In a knowledge-based economy, organisations worldwide need to attract, motivate, and retain the best employees. Human capital – a talented and quality workforce – has a remarkable value for creating sustainable competitive advantages. Being perceived as an attractive employer to highly qualified employees is an important goal for organisations worldwide. Talented people are a competitive advantage for organisations, but at the same time, they are scarce. Mobility of the highly-skilled workforce and short term commitment are realities in today's organisations. In this context, the authors outline the importance of implementing policies, practices and activities that can strengthen the organisational talent pool “imperatives” upon which these companies were founded. CSR can be used as a lever for talent management. Corporate social responsibility practices impact human resource (HR) functioning and influence employee recruiting, selecting, and retaining (Turner et al., 2019). Considering those job seekers are often interested in socially responsible firms, corporate social responsibility (CRS) is important in labour market communication (Klimkiewicz & Oltra, 2017). Moreover, the perceptions of the employees and job applicants regarding the firm's CSR policies, activities and initiatives determine their interest in the respective organisation.

The Institute for Employment Studies have reviewed websites of different organisations from both private and public sectors and outlined some representative concerns regarding the workplace concern: communication and collaboration; training, lifelong learning, skills and career development; health and safety at work; social protection and security of employment; work-life balance; equality and diversity; pay and other rewards; representation and voice; flexibility (Wright et al., 2018). It is important to emphasise that corporate social responsibility practices and activities can be important antecedents to improve workplace attitudes. Workplace practices are an integral part of the organisation, being crucial for the productivity growth and competitiveness of the organisation. At the same time, workplace practices are inevitable aspects of CSR.

Employees contribute with skills, knowledge, and experience to their organisations' performance and, in exchange, organisations should fulfill their needs. In this sense, companies should look at employees from the stakeholder theory perspective and consider their requests (Harwood et al., 2008). By fulfilling employee needs, corporate social initiatives can serve as a highly effective component of internal marketing programs (Hildebrand et al., 2011). In the Chapter “Business and employees”, DesJardins and McCall outline the importance of respecting critical aspects such: job security and participation, health and safety, equal treatment to the workplace, free expression, privacy in the workplace, ethical responsibilities in business – honesty, loyalty, trust, conflicts of interest (DesJardins & McCall, 2014).

Regarding the workplace – as an internal dimension of corporate social responsibility (I-CSR) – some multiple practices and activities are socially responsible: responsible recruitment and

selection – non-discrimination/ fair practice; greater workforce diversity; equality planning and implementation; health and safety workplace; socially responsible restructuring; better balance between work, family, and leisure; concern for employability and workplace security; profit sharing; training opportunities and professional development; empowerment of employees; promotion perspectives; career development opportunities; transparency and better information flow; no discriminatory harassment; fair and reasonable procedures for termination of employment. Addressing issues related to moral guidelines of corporations, Frederick stressed, since 1991, some fundamental employment practices and activities: job stability and security; equal pay for equal work; freedom of association; non-discrimination; equal job opportunities; favourable work conditions; healthful and safe work standards and conditions; protection against unemployment; employee upgrade through training.

Health and safety policies, activities and practices purpose is to protect people. Providing a safe and healthy workplace is an important goal for every organisation. Employees' injuries and illnesses are expensive – involving direct and indirect short-term and long-term costs. In this context, employee health and safety should become a top priority for every organisation. As a multidisciplinary field, Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) is concerned with health, safety, and welfare issues. OHS is not a fad but a must for all types of organisations that aim to improve their working environment. Such activities have to be developed as part of the continual improvement process. Purely by their nature, all OHS activities are part of the corporate social responsibility. Always issues like safety and health at work find an important place within CSR. Companies recognise that social performance is crucial to be good externally (EU-OSHA, 2004). Moreover, we have to emphasise the fact that workplace safety requires constant teamwork. It is important not only to implement appropriate practices and activities but also to develop safety-oriented behaviour.

Organisations should treat employees fairly in order to motivate, engage and retain them. Within the seven (7) central issues reflected by the ISO 26000 standard, especially “Human Rights” and “Labor Practices”, contain workplace CSR aspects with high relevance for employees. Health and safety conditions, work-life balance, general wellbeing, flexible working, pay and benefits, training, education scholarships, promotion are only some of the CSR practices that act as relevant, motivating factors for employees, enhancing job satisfaction (Chepkwony et al., 2015). Fair employment practices are also very important to motivate employees. Nowadays, most people want much more out of a job than high pay and comprehensive benefits. Non-monetary rewards such as career development, work-life balance, participation in decision making, job security, job recognition, educational benefits, promotional opportunities can enhance the satisfaction level of employees (Haider et al., 2015).

Considering that companies' product and service quality depends on their employees, it is obvious that their training is essential. Employees' career paths and succession planning are important ingredients for a win-win human resource strategy and initiatives that could motivate loyal and productive employees. Most CSR activities and practices affect the field of human resources. Based on theoretical analysis on available literature regarding CSR and workplace, on CSR reporting practices and CSR standards (ISO 26000), we identified possible issues, practices, actions, and attributes relating to the workplace dimension of CSR. In the following paragraphs, we present some of our findings: responsible recruitment and selection; responsible/ fair remuneration/ fair wages and benefits packages/ fair and honorable pay/ compensation and benefits/ competitive pay; fair treatment at work; respecting human rights/ respecting the rights of employees; training

and learning/ creating learning opportunities; personal and professional development/ human development/ opportunity for personal satisfaction and professional development; career progression; performance management; diversity/equal opportunity; health and safety at work/ safe and healthy working environment/ workplace security; job security; ergonomics/ conditions of work; respectful work environment; social benefits/ social protection/ support of employees & family members; attitude towards disadvantaged groups; succession planning; socially responsible restructuring/responsible approach in restructuring in case of crisis; pensions/early retirement incentives/responsible retirement; labour relations/internal relationships/ relationships with co-workers/ employment relationships/ freedom of association/ social dialogue/ employee representation; opportunities for participation in decision making/ employee involvement; employee communication and consultation; flexible working hour, employee wellbeing/ quality of life; work-life balance, etc.

Improving employee quality of life has become a strategic issue. Advancing human wellbeing is at the core of the transformation towards sustainable development (Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2019). Employees are communication channels, both internal and external. They can transmit valuable information regarding the companies' values, behaviours, expectations. There is a close link between internal branding and employee satisfaction, loyalty, engagement and retention (Lee et al., 2014; Dechawatanapaisal, 2018). Employees' commitment and positive attitude regarding workplace quality could generate important benefits and contribute to a competitive advantage for the respective organisation. An organisation that conduct CSR practices – especially regarding the workplace dimension – and who create a culture of responsibility among managers and employees will nurture and foster engagement and retention of the best employees.

Cohen outlines that Human Resources (HR) is a critical partner for CSR, and human resource managers should create and maintain a responsible workplace. In this context, the author presents some responsible practices and actions: employee dialogue and engagement; employee rights; rewards and recognition; wellbeing; health and safety; training and development; and communication (Cohen, 2010).

Study on the workplace-related CSR practices/ activities implemented in companies from centre region, Romania. Research methodology

As outlined before, corporate social responsibility (CSR) covers four fields/ areas or dimensions: environmental, workplace, marketplace, and community. The present research, focused on the workplace area of CSR, was undertaken as a continuation of another comprehensive study conducted in 2016 regarding leadership, ethics and CSR. One of the study's objectives was to assess the attitude of managers from private companies regarding CSR practices/ activities in general and in their companies in particular. In one section of our questionnaire, using Likert's five-point scale, respondents indicated the importance of each CSR field/ area/ domain: workplace, marketplace, community and environment (anchored as 1=Not important and 5=Very important). Our research emphasised that the Workplace (with the calculated score=4.16) was the most important for respondents, closely followed by the Marketplace (4.12). As we concluded, leaders understood the importance of the workplace environment for recruiting, motivating, and retaining the best employees (Gorski, 2017). In this regard, we consider that it is opportune to continue detailing our investigation. As a result, in 2019, we undertook the current research whose partial results we are presenting in our paper.

Data collection, sample selection, research process, and data analyses

The present paper aims to identify how internal corporate social responsibility (CSR) practices/ initiatives/ activities related to the workplace are implemented in organisations from Center Region, Romania. For data collection regarding our topics, primary and secondary researches have been used. We started with the secondary research – studying published materials and existing literature – and continued with the primary research, based on a self-administrated questionnaire.

The statistical population consists of managers and experts – with significant knowledge regarding this subject – from different organisations in the Centre Development Region, Romania (making up 14.3% of the country's territory), which includes six (6) counties: Alba, Brasov, Covasna, Harghita, and Sibiu. The statistical population for our study covers a wide range of organisations (microenterprises, SMEs, and large firms), including different types of business industries and forms of capital (Romanian capital, foreign, mixed).

The disproportionate variant and the availability/convenience sampling method have been used for our study. The research hypotheses were tested using a questionnaire. To identify the extent to which organisations have adopted specific workplace CSR policies, activities and practices, a 5-point Likert scale was used (anchored as 1=Strongly Disagree and 5=Strongly Agree). Before survey deployment, the questionnaire was reviewed with a group of three experts familiar with our topic. Afterwards, we have run a pilot test using a subset of our total population (6 representatives). The participants in our study were contacted through an e-mail with the invitation to complete the online survey. Collected data were processed and analysed, and hypotheses tested using the SPSS Statistics software package.

Research limitations

In order to ensure the veracity of the study, it is important to highlight some of the limitations. First is the generalisation limitation due to the method used for sampling—convenience sample. Considering the aspects mentioned above, our findings cannot be generalised to the total population of companies from the Centre region, Romania. Second, our results are based on manager and expert evaluations, not on real behaviour. The collected data reflects how managers evaluate CSR policies, practices, and activities regarding the workplace but cannot assess to what extent these are related to the real situation. We can only suppose that the respondents provide accurate information regarding these issues.

Findings

After processing data collected from the respondents, we can present some of our results regarding the extent to which CSR practices/ activities/ initiatives are implemented in the surveyed companies. For the analysis and presentation, the investigated elements were coded as follows: WKCSR1, WKCSR2, etc. (WK = Workplace, CSR = Corporate Social Responsibility).

- *WKCSR1*– The recruitment and selection policy is based on non-discriminatory principles, is transparent, and congruent to appropriate criteria.
- *WKCSR2*- The remuneration policy (wages and salaries) is clear, transparent, and related to employee skills, competencies, and performance.
- *WKCSR3*- Emphasis is placed on Career Planning/ Career Management (including promotion within the organisation).

- *WKCSR4*- Ensures skill enhancement & Employee training and development (Lifelong Learning – LLL).
- *WKCSR5* - Ensures employability and job security; Job rotation is promoted.
- *WKCSR6* - Ensures a healthy and safe working environment (workplace).
- *WKCSR7*-Incentives are deployed to stimulate responsibility, motivation, creativity, innovation of employees.
- *WKCSR8*-Flexible management and working hours, as well as teleworking/ telecommuting, are promoted.
- *WKCSR9*- Socially responsible restructuring/ responsible approach in restructuring in case of a crisis is applied.
- *WKCSR10*- Facilitates the conciliation of employees’ professional and personal life/ Balance of working and family life/ Work-life balance.
- *WKCSR11* - Incorporates CSR practices in the rewards and recognition system to involve employees in achieving social and environmental objectives.

The findings of our survey reflect several aspects. As we can observe in figure 1, the highest score calculated on the Likert scale was for *WKCSR6* - healthy and safe working environment (4.4), followed closely by *WKCSR1* - recruitment and selection policy based on non-discriminatory principles, transparent and congruent to appropriate criteria (4.35), and *WKCSR2* – fair and transparent remuneration, related to skills, competencies, and performance (4.2). The other three items were ranked between 3 and 4, but more closely to 4 (on the Likert scale between “Neutral” and “Agree”, match closer to “Agree”). Following, we found *WKCSR4* – skills enhancement & employees’ training and development (3.85), *WKCSR7* - incentives to ensure responsibility, motivation, creativity, innovation of employees are deployed (3.81), and *WKCSR3*–career management (3.71). Our research reveals that four items were also ranked between 3 and 4. However, more closely to 3 („Neutral” on Likert scale): *WKCSR5* - employability, job security & job rotation is promoted (3.47), *WKCSR9* - socially responsible restructuring/ responsible approach in restructuring in case of crisis (3.27), *WKCSR8* – flexible management and working hours, as well as teleworking (3.2), and *WKCSR10* – Work-Life balance approach (3.1). *WKCSR11* – CSR practices incorporated in the rewards and recognition system was evaluated at the lowest score (2.55). This result emphasises that researched companies are not aware that CSR practices could enhance employee motivation and performances. The majority of the respondents do not appreciate the importance of integrating CSR standards in their reward and recognition programs.

Figure 1: Workplace – CSR initiatives/ practices/ activities

Conclusions and recommendations

This paper provides both a theoretical and a practical framework for analysing the workplace dimension of CSR. As we emphasised before, the present research aimed to identify how CSR activities, practices, and initiatives regarding the workplace are implemented in companies from the Centre Region, Romania. The paper concludes with findings and recommendations relevant to managers and experts from the CSR and HR fields. We anticipate that our findings will bring more light on CSR workplace practices that can be integrated into the business sustainability strategy and generate long-term added value not only for their organisation and their stakeholders but also for society and the environment.

Findings from our study revealed that the investigated companies are only aware of some aspects regarding this CSR domain (as we previously emphasised with the scores calculated on the Likert scale above 4). Concern for creating a continuous learning environment does not rise to an appropriate level for the knowledge-based economy. Unfortunately, we found a lack of methods, practices, and activities for career planning and career development. Many managers are not interested in fully understanding employee needs regarding training, growth and career development and are reluctant to a learner-centric professional development. Their reasons are different, but all involve a certain degree of parsimony. Some of the respondents – especially from micro and small enterprises – claim that they have no time and financial resources to invest in these types of practices. Also, many argue that if they invest too much in employee development, these will demand higher wages or even go to another employer who pays them better.

Another important aspect that we want to highlight is that the investigated companies do not understand that it is their responsibility to implement practices that reduce the work-related stress level of employees. Stress and Work-life balance are interlinked. Nowadays, there is a growing level of occupational stress in any organisation, especially in the private sector. However, stressful job conditions and work-life imbalance can be found in many companies. Unfortunately, companies that participated in our study do not offer solid work-life balance policies and practices in addition to their remuneration packages. Work-life benefits are not deployed for consolidating these values in the organisational culture.

Moreover, a work-life balance culture is almost nonexistent in the investigated companies. It is important to stress that competitive labour market companies can better attract, motivate, and retain highly qualified employees by creating a healthy working environment and an organisational culture that supports working-time agreements and work-life balance. Finding a balance between working and private life could reduce stress and health problems and contribute to employee wellbeing.

Based on our experience combined with both the theoretical and the empirical analysis, our paper concludes with a set of recommendations:

- Flexible working arrangements/Flexible work programs (e.g. telecommuting, remote working, compressed workweeks, part-time hours, flexible schedule, customised working hours). This approach could generate multiple advantages for employers and employees (job satisfaction, less stress, work-life balance)
- Integrate CSR in the job description, recruitment, selection criteria, performance appraisal methods, and reward and recognition systems. CSR policies should be designed to encourage employees' engagement in specific environmental and social sustainability practices.

- Skills and competencies development programs for all employees & Career planning and development opportunities – not only increase employee productivity but also impact job satisfaction. Career development and lifelong learning (LLL) go hand in hand and represent important issues for organisations regarding the workplace dimension of CSR. Responsibility for career management should be shared between employees and organisations. As a result, we can emphasise the employers' responsibility to develop and implement career management policies, with concrete procedures, activities, and initiatives to communicate that they appreciate and reward employee learning and development. Managers should implement formal and informal training programs (mentoring, coaching, counselling, job shadowing, job rotation) to enhance employee skills and competencies. These actions should encourage employees to be involved in continuous learning for their personal and professional development. In addition to career management, succession planning/succession management is another important aspect that organisations should integrate into CSR policies.
- Work-Life Balance programs should be implemented to prevent injuries and illnesses, enhance employee satisfaction, physical and mental health, and implicitly improve their job performance. We are living and working in stressful times, characterised by unpredictable and fast changes. Employee wellbeing is a shared responsibility of both the organisation and their employees. Managers must understand that employees are not robots, they are first and foremost human, and so they need special care. As an essential component of workplace wellness, Work-Life Balance programs can prevent burnout and reduce stress.
- Socially responsible restructuring programs. Under different pressures and changes that are taking place both in the organisational and/or external environment, sometimes companies need to be restructured or revamped in order to succeed and/or even to survive. Restructuring is a complex process that can have a harmful impact on the health and wellbeing of employees. Job loss that often accompanies the restructuring process can generate health problems, unfortunately often hard to cure - depression, anxiety, psychological distress. Times of crisis are characterised by unpredictability and uncertainty. Mostly, crises generate shocks and trauma with immediate and long-term effects on people wellbeing. Considering these major implications, companies need to deploy a responsible approach in restructuring in times of crisis. A supportive working environment is important, especially in difficult times. Commitment to supporting employees financially and even emotionally should be part of responsible workplace practices and should be integrated into practical CSR actions and initiatives.

The Human Resources (HR) function has a critical role in strengthening CSR values regarding the workplace dimension and the marketplace, environment, and community dimensions. The HR and CSR managers and/or experts who implement corporate social responsibility in the workplace should have a long term-perspective regarding the consequences of their policies, practices, and activities. It is important to understand that highly qualified people are motivated not only by financial rewards but also by other factors such as career development, stress management, work-life balance, flexible work hours and other ingredients that can contribute to human welfare.

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Conflict of Interests

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